

1 **Kinase and phosphatase inhibition as a signal transduction-centric approach to adjunctive**
2 **chemotherapies for the treatment of gynecologic cancers: PPME1.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 Men and women differ in large part resulting from the presence or absence of gynecologic organs
8 including the ovaries, the uterus, the lining of which is known as the endometrium, and the entry to the
9 uterus (womb), the cervix (1), all of which are targets for development of malignancies (2-7); vulvar
10 cancer is less common (8). Cancer, or unrestricted cell division which develops into a tumor after
11 remaining unchecked, evades active cell death and cell cycle control mechanisms, sustaining its survival
12 through growth factor signals (9) which are transduced to the nucleus to activate and repress transcription
13 of genes (10, 11). These signals are transduced between the plasma membrane and the nucleus by the
14 action of kinases and phosphatases, enzymes that utilize conformational changes and a catalytic site to
15 translate a signal from the extracellular environment to a change in gene expression. Catalytic sites are
16 pharmacologically targetable, and small molecule targeting of the appropriate kinase or phosphatase target
17 will disrupt or block this transduction (12, 13). We utilized whole transcriptome technologies (14, 15) to
18 identify and validate kinase and phosphatase targets in gynecologic oncology, including cancer of the
19 lining of the uterus, or endometrial cancer. Here we describe a differentially expressed, up-regulated, and
20 catalytically available phosphatase target in endometrial cancer: PPME1.

21
22
23
24
25
26
27 **Keywords:** kinase, phosphatase, signal transduction, gynecologic oncology, therapeutic targets in cancer,
28 chemical biology, systems biology of human cancer.

1 We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the
2 transcriptome (RNA), the proteome (total collection of proteins in the cell) and epigenetic modification
3 (eg., CpG-DNA) of human cancer (16-20). This includes the primary tumor, the source of the
4 transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - cancer subtypes, like adeno and squamous forms of
5 non-small cell lung cancer, metastasis to distant sites, including the lymph nodes, the lungs, the liver, the
6 brain, and bones, and the circulating tumor stem cell, which emerges from the primary tumor, disseminates
7 through the body and establishes a novel entity in a separate organ (21-26).

8 Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and
9 therapeutic limitations are best managed using identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome
10 differential expression analyses (subtraction analysis), administered in combination with FDA approved
11 broad-spectrum chemotherapeutics like CDK4/6 inhibitors, and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully
12 complemented by reverse genetic screening strategies (27, 28) to blindly identify disease-specific,
13 subtype-specific and metastasis-specific therapeutic vulnerabilities, fully augmented by novel
14 immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe a phosphatase therapeutic target identified through
15 rigorous study of the endometrial tumor transcriptome: a phosphatase target that is up-regulated and
16 catalytically available: PPME1.

17 Results

18 **Figure 1:** PPME1 is differentially expressed in endometrial cancer.

19 I. Primary tumors of the endometrium from humans with endometrial cancer.

20 $n=5$ normal endometrial tissue

21 $n=7$ primary tumors (endometrium; human)

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
49077_at	3.31E-02	-2.4031204	-3.82196	-0.42976079	PPME1	4059/22277	81.8

22 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the normal endometrial tissue and in
23 primary tumors of humans with endometrial cancer (14), we discovered differential expression of protein
24 phosphatase methylesterase 1, encoded by *PPME1* in endometrial cancer in humans (**Chart 1**). The
25 expression of PPME1 changed more than 80% of the human endometrial tumor transcriptome when
26 considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,277 transcripts (“Rank”).
27 Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PPME1 messenger RNA in endometrial
28 tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of PPME1 during transformation of the endometrium.

Thus, differential and increased expression of PPME1 defines the transcriptional landscape of
endometrial cancer in humans.

Discussion

Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy). Small
molecule inhibitors of PPME1 phosphatase, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately be
tested for efficacy in patients with endometrial cancer, with the goal of identifying the most effective
phosphatase inhibitors for management of gynecologic malignancies. An approach that combines kinase
and phosphatase targeting with a recently described multi-catalytic strategy that targets dNTP synthesis,

1 replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, likely delivered in conjunction
2 with standard chemotherapies and drug resistance pump inhibitors in resistant cases, is most likely to be
3 most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance and disease (29).
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

References

1. Hacker, N.F., Gambone, J.C. and Hobel, C.J., 2015. *Hacker & Moore's essentials of obstetrics and gynecology*. Elsevier Health Sciences.
2. Matulonis, U.A., Sood, A.K., Fallowfield, L., Howitt, B.E., Sehouli, J. and Karlan, B.Y., 2016. Ovarian cancer. *Nature reviews Disease primers*, 2(1), pp.1-22.
3. Veneziani, A.C., Gonzalez-Ochoa, E., Alqaisi, H., Madariaga, A., Bhat, G., Rouzbahman, M., Sneha, S. and Oza, A.M., 2023. Heterogeneity and treatment landscape of ovarian carcinoma. *Nature Reviews Clinical Oncology*, 20(12), pp.820-842.
4. Makker, V., MacKay, H., Ray-Coquard, I., Levine, D.A., Westin, S.N., Aoki, D. and Oaknin, A., 2021. Endometrial cancer. *Nature reviews Disease primers*, 7(1), p.88.
5. Urlick, M.E. and Bell, D.W., 2019. Clinical actionability of molecular targets in endometrial cancer. *Nature Reviews Cancer*, 19(9), pp.510-521.
6. Frazer, I.H., 2004. Prevention of cervical cancer through papillomavirus vaccination. *Nature Reviews Immunology*, 4(1), pp.46-55.
7. Alfaro, K., Maza, M., Cremer, M., Masch, R. and Soler, M., 2021. Removing global barriers to cervical cancer prevention and moving towards elimination. *Nature Reviews Cancer*, 21(10), pp.607-608.
8. Li, Z., Liu, P., Wang, Z., Zhang, Z., Chen, Z., Chu, R., Li, G., Han, Q., Zhao, Y., Li, L. and Miao, J., 2023. Prevalence of human papillomavirus DNA and p16INK4a positivity in vulvar cancer and vulvar intraepithelial neoplasia: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *The Lancet Oncology*, 24(4), pp.403-414
9. Hanahan, D. and Weinberg, R.A., 2000. The hallmarks of cancer. *cell*, 100(1), pp.57-70.
10. Zhang, J., Yang, P.L. and Gray, N.S., 2009. Targeting cancer with small molecule kinase inhibitors. *Nature reviews cancer*, 9(1), pp.28-39.
11. Vainonen, J.P., Momeny, M. and Westermarck, J., 2021. Druggable cancer phosphatases. *Science translational medicine*, 13(588), p.eabe2967.
12. Brivanlou, A.H. and Darnell Jr, J.E., 2002. Signal transduction and the control of gene expression. *Science*, 295(5556), pp.813-818.
13. Sever, R. and Brugge, J.S., 2015. Signal transduction in cancer. *Cold Spring Harbor perspectives in medicine*, 5(4), p.a006098.
14. Pappa, K.I., Polyzos, A., Jacob-Hirsch, J., Amariglio, N., Vlachos, G.D., Loutradis, D. and Anagnou, N.P., 2015. Profiling of discrete gynecological cancers reveals novel transcriptional modules and common features shared by other cancer types and embryonic stem cells. *PLoS one*, 10(11), p.e0142229.
15. GSE39099. Wei-Yun Huang. Department of Biological Sciences and Technology. NCTU. Taiwan.
16. Kirschner, M.W., 2005. The meaning of systems biology. *Cell*, 121(4), pp.503-504.
17. Gehlenborg, N., O'donoghue, S.I., Baliga, N.S., Goesmann, A., Hibbs, M.A., Kitano, H., Kohlbacher, O., Neuweger, H., Schneider, R., Tenenbaum, D. and Gavin, A.C., 2010. Visualization of omics data for systems biology. *Nature methods*, 7(Suppl 3), pp.S56-S68.
18. Fitzgerald, J.B., Schoeberl, B., Nielsen, U.B. and Sorger, P.K., 2006. Systems biology and combination therapy in the quest for clinical efficacy. *Nature chemical biology*, 2(9), pp.458-466.
19. Butcher, E.C., Berg, E.L. and Kunkel, E.J., 2004. Systems biology in drug discovery. *Nature biotechnology*, 22(10), pp.1253-1259.
20. Dey, S.S., Kester, L., Spanjaard, B., Bienko, M. and Van Oudenaarden, A., 2015. Integrated genome and transcriptome sequencing of the same cell. *Nature biotechnology*, 33(3), pp.285-289.
21. Eliyahu, D., Raz, A., Gruss, P., Givol, D. and Oren, M., 1984. Participation of p53 cellular tumour antigen in transformation of normal embryonic cells. *Nature*, 312(5995), pp.646-649.
22. Sims, A.H., Howell, A., Howell, S.J. and Clarke, R.B., 2007. Origins of breast cancer subtypes and therapeutic implications. *Nature Clinical Practice Oncology*, 4(9), pp.516-525.

1 23. Chaffer, C.L. and Weinberg, R.A., 2011. A perspective on cancer cell metastasis. *science*,
2 331(6024), pp.1559-1564.

3 24. Reya, T., Morrison, S.J., Clarke, M.F. and Weissman, I.L., 2001. Stem cells, cancer, and cancer
4 stem cells. *nature*, 414(6859), pp.105-111.

5 25. Battle, E. and Clevers, H., 2017. Cancer stem cells revisited. *Nature medicine*, 23(10),
6 pp.1124-1134.

7 26. Kreso, A. and Dick, J.E., 2014. Evolution of the cancer stem cell model. *Cell stem cell*, 14(3),
8 pp.275-291.

9 27. Koike-Yusa, H., Li, Y., Tan, E.P., Velasco-Herrera, M.D.C. and Yusa, K., 2014. Genome-wide
10 recessive genetic screening in mammalian cells with a lentiviral CRISPR-guide RNA library. *Nature*
11 *biotechnology*, 32(3), pp.267-273.

12 28. Shah, A.N., Davey, C.F., Whitebirch, A.C., Miller, A.C. and Moens, C.B., 2015. Rapid reverse
13 genetic screening using CRISPR in zebrafish. *Nature methods*, 12(6), pp.535-540.

14 29. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Therapeutic targeting of catalytically available solid tumor vulnerabilities
15 in human cancer.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We utilized GSE63678 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in primary tumors from humans with endometrial cancer, as compared to normal endometrium (along with GSE39099 for target validation) using microarray data (published or public) and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).